

**STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF COMPLEX SENTENCES USING THE EXAMPLE OF
ABDULLAH QAHHOR'S STORY "THIEF"**

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ANNOTATION

This article talks about complex sentences taught in the native language, their types and situations of use, and such sentences are highlighted using the example of the story "The Thief" by Abdullah Kahhor .

Key words: sentence, simple sentence, complex sentence, thief, Abdullah Kahhor , non-compound sentence, coherent sentence, subordinate clause, contradiction, connection of loneliness.

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This article talks about compound sentences taught in the mother tongue, their types and situations of use, and such sentences are highlighted on the example of the story "Thief" by Abdulla Qahhor.

Key words: sentence, simple sentence, compound sentence, thief, Abdulla Qa hhor, non-conjunctive clause, connected clause, subordinate clause, contradiction, bond loneliness.

ANNOTATION

This article talks about complex sentences taught in the native language, their types and situations of use, and such sentences are highlighted using the example of the story "The Thief" by Abdullah Kahhor .

Key words: sentence, simple sentence, complex sentence, thief, Abdullah Kahhor , non-compound sentence, coherent sentence, subordinate clause, contradiction, connection of loneliness.

Connection __ offers in teaching, English _ first of all , him how to be __ And How harvest be __ see __ tooth __ this is acceptable . *One cut to the sign , significant And tone until completion have was __ talk simple , two or From him more than simple talk mutual __ grammar And essential from relationships organize found , tone until completion have was __ integrity connection __ talk counts .*

An important sign of judgment is the cross. The number of sentences is the basis for dividing sentences into simple and complex sentences. For example: I am a student - a simple sentence; If you are a scientist, your world is a complex sentence . [N.M. Makhmudova, A. Nurmonov , A. Sh. Sobirov . Textbook for 9th grade of secondary school. Tashkent publishing house " Tasvir ", 2014. Page 15]

So, the difference between a simple sentence and a complex sentence lies in their verb forms. Writer Abdullah Kahhor used conjunctions effectively in his short story “The Thief.” First, we will identify all the conjunctions used in the story and then analyze each of them. They are as follows:

1. Oh!.. There is no ox, the bull is pierced from the street...
2. Let the farmer's house burn, and let not his ox perish.
3. To find a bag of straw, fifteen poles, a cart of reeds, a house and an ox, you need to lower the pot into water several times.
4. People are accustomed to the sounds of thunder: someone’s husband beats them, someone’s house falls like a letter...
5. Grandfather Cain, with his head uncovered and bare feet, stands at the door of a lonely boy, trembling, his knees buckling; his eyes widen, he looks at everyone, but sees no one.
6. Women curse the thief, dogs bark, chickens crow.
7. He entered the stable and carefully examined the pit, the post to which the ox was tied; For some reason he saw the movement of the pillar, then he called grandfather Cain and said in a quiet voice:
8. Your ox will not go anywhere, they will find it.
9. His visit to the manger gave great hope to Grandfather Cain, which made him very happy.
10. Don't cry, I say don't cry!

11. Your ox will be found if it has not escaped from the hand of the white horse.
12. The centurion put the ox in a large amount of cash - as if he goes outside, they will find the ox.
13. Grandfather Cain tapped his wallet, gave everything he had for fifty and prayed for how much more.
14. The dry spoon is tearing my mouth, how much money can I take to Amin?
15. One is too much to give, and ten is too little to take.
16. The old man and the old woman agreed: this is the last way out and the one that ties the ox by the neck, so it is unwise to look money in the face.
17. When Grandfather Cain appeared in front of him, Amin stuttered loudly without opening his mouth, then laughed, lowering his chin.
18. - Was it a good bull or a bad ox?
19. Although it is not written that if someone takes it, come back!
20. Shall we look? - said Amin, wiping his chin with his shoe, - what will happen to the supporter?
21. "Don't talk," he said, handing over the money, "I'm at your service again."
22. This week the old woman brought half a bag of rice, three bowls of corn and two skeins of yarn to Azaim Khan, who "opens locks with the power of prayer," but it did not work.
23. After all, let him go and let him complain!
24. Grandfather Cain consulted with his friends - what can be taken to the bailiff, except money?
25. It became known that a person's back would break before he was called begum .
26. Tilmokh took the bag and immediately promised to give the bailiff detailed explanations.
27. All the old man's joints became loose, and then he fell asleep, but could he say anything to his grave!
28. "With a character you can't play with - he hits you in every chapter."
29. -Tell me your suspicions! - said the centurion, - "If I don't know who took it, if I'm not a saint!"

30. If you don't tell me for a long time, if you don't melt, go to the tannery and look at the skins.
31. And if the skin catches fire, then it has already become skin; God knows if it hit the market like kavush ...
32. If there is only one ox, it will be one, God give me a chance to die!
33. I will tell my mother-in-law to give you an ox.
34. Pakhtafurush took great pity on the old man and gave him not one, but two oxen, which plowed the land, but with the condition "only a small one." [*Abdullah Kahhor . Who is guilty? Stories. "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan". State publishing house. Tashkent-2018. pp. 20-23*]

Based on the way their parts are connected and the semantic relationship, three types of complex sentences are distinguished: 1) a coherent complex sentence; 2) next union; 3) union without union.

Compare: Talent is always different, but talent is the same everywhere. (E. Vakhidov)
We want to say that a person should always thirst for knowledge. (F. Giulio Curie). [*M. Khamroev , D. Mukhamedova , D. Shodmonkulova , Kh. Gulomova , Sh. Yoldosheva . Native language. Tashkent "Economics-Finance" 2007. P. 225*]

The components of a complex sentence are connected using a word in the function of a connective or connecting word or without them at all. Based on this, it will be possible to divide unions into unions with and without unions. The conjunction is divided into a conjunction connected by a grammatical means, a conjunction connected by a lexical-grammatical means, and a conjunction connected by a lexical means. According to the function of the adverb, a distinction is made between a conjunction with an equal conjunction and a conjunction with the following conjunction . *Modern Uzbek literary language. Tashkent-2009. p. 398*).

So, we will study complex sentences in three groups. This:

- 1) coherent sentences;
- 2) the following unions;
- 3) unions without reference.

We classify the individual sentences from Abdullah Kahhor's story "The Thief" one by one as stated above. First of all, we will describe a coherent sentence and quote the sentences associated with it. Coherent sentences include complex sentences that are formed by entering

into equal relationships with each other. If yes, then they are connected by words and equal conjunctions:

a) Was it a good ox or a bad ox?

b) During this week, the old woman brought half a bag of rice, three bowls of oats and two kalaws of yarn to Azaim Khan, who “opens the lock with the power of prayer,” but it did not work.

d) Tilmokh took the bag and immediately promised to explain everything in detail to the bailiff.

Participles of conjunctions are formed with the conjunction and are in the participial or participial form, usually in the same tense form, and indicate the state of an action that occurs or does not occur simultaneously or one after the other. [HOUR. Dzhamalkhanov . Modern Uzbek literary language. Tashkent – “ Talkin ” – 2005 p. 396]

The above conjunctions are connected by equal conjunctions (or, but, and).

The following conjunctions are joined by the following conjunctions, conditionals (-ca) , auxiliaries and prepositions -ki :

a) It became known that a person’s back was broken until they called him “ running .”

b) If you don’t tell me for a long time, if you don’t melt, go to the tannery and look at the skins.

d) The centurion put the ox in cash - as if he went out into the street and the ox was found.

In the third type, that is, in unions without connectors, the parts are connected only in tone and content. Sentences are separated by commas, hyphens and colons:

a) If a farmer’s house burns down, let not his ox perish.

b) How many times will it be necessary to lower the pot into the water to find a bag of straw, fifteen poles, a cart of reeds, a house and an ox.

d) Your ox will not go anywhere, they will find it.

e) The visit to the estate instilled hope in Grandfather Cain, which made him very happy.

e) Don't cry, I say don't cry!

g) Grandfather Cain rummaged in his wallet, gave everything he had for fifty heads, and prayed for how long.

h) A dry spoon is tearing my mouth, how much money can I take to Amin?

- i) One more for the giver than ten less for the receiver.
- j) When Grandfather Cain appeared in front of him, Amin stuttered loudly without opening his mouth, and then laughed, lowering his chin.
- j) After all, let him go and complain!
- k) Grandfather Cain consulted with his friends - what can be taken to the bailiff, except money?
- m) "Don't play with the character - he will beat you in every chapter."
- o) If there were only one ox, then there would be one, God, let me die!
- o) I will tell my mother-in-law to give you an ox.
- p) There is no bull, the street is broken from the side of the bull.

In addition, complex sentences and sentences with quotations are also actively involved in the work.

Based on the number of components, two types of conjunctions are distinguished: 1) two-component conjunctions (see discussion of connected, subsequent, non-connective conjunctions), 2) multi-component (complex) complex sentences.

Multicomponent (complex) complex sentences are formed from the content and grammatical combination of three or more components [M. Khamroev , D. Mukhamedova , D. Shodmonkulova , Kh. Gulomova , Sh. Yoldasheva . Native language. Tashkent "Economics-Finance" 2007. P. 239]:

- a) People are accustomed to the sound dod : someone's husband beats someone, someone's house falls into the letter...
- b) Grandfather Cain, bareheaded, barefoot, stands at the door of a lonely boy, trembling violently, his knees buckling. his eyes widen, he looks at everyone, but sees no one.
- d) Women curse the thief, dogs bark, chickens crow.
- e) He entered the stable and carefully examined the pit, the post to which the ox was tied; For some reason he saw the movement of the pillar, then he called grandfather Cain and said in a quiet voice:
- f) The old man and the old woman made a decision: this is the last way out and the one that ties the bull by the neck, so it is unwise to face money.
- g) All the old man's joints became loose, and then he fell asleep, but could he say anything to his grave!

h) And if the skin is tanned , then it has already become leather; God knows if it hit the market like kavush ...

i) Pakhtafurush took great pity on the old man, plowed his land and gave not one, but two oxen, but with the condition “only a small one.”

Prepositional phrases:

a) - Shall we search? - said Amin, wiping his chin with his shoe, - what will happen to the supporter?

b) “Don’t talk,” he said, handing over the money, “I’m at your service again.”

d) - If not, tell me about your suspicions! - said the centurion: “If I don’t know who took it, if I’m not a saint.”

In conclusion , we can say that Abdullah Kahhor has effectively used complex sentences in this work and it is through this work that the topic of complex sentences can be fully explored.

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